

TEACHER COMPONENT AND PARENTAL PARTICIPATION IMPACTS ON SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS' ACADEMIC OUTCOME IN IFO LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF OGUN STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study examined teacher component and parental participation impact on senior secondary school student academic outcome in Ifo local government area of Ogun state, Nigeria. The study adopted the descriptive survey research design type. 250 respondents comprising of fifty (50) teachers and two hundred (200) students were sampled using stratified sampling technique. The instruments used in the study for data collection were “Teacher Component and Parental Participation Impact on Student Academic Outcome” (TCPPISAO) and student academic outcome Test (SAOT). Four hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The Data that was collected were analysed with simple percentage and Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient at 0.05 level of significance. The sub-variables that enhanced student academic outcome are teacher components, classroom management, class control, teaching experience and instructional skills while the other variable of parental participation and teacher certification are not great determinants of student academic outcome. This study can be used to enlighten the educational stakeholders and planners on the need for qualified teachers to enhance adequate teaching and learning in secondary schools in Ogun State and Nigeria at large. Ogun State students can make great academic growth if their parents are consistent in their support to attain academic goals and aspirations.

Introduction

Academic outcome is the assessment of education goal. That is, the extent to which a student or school has achieved their educational objective. Rafiei (2019) perceived academic outcome as one of the potent measures used to rate any educational system. It connotes the extent to which students have learnt a given task. The impact on teachers could be beneficial or a barrier to learning and teaching. According to Orimoloye (2015) held that the quality of education in Nigeria was deteriorating and thus militating against achieving the national policy on education

(FRN, 2014). Teachers' component is an important factor to be considered in ascertaining students' academic outcome as far senior secondary school is concerned.

Celebi et al (2020) opined that teachers' component in students' academic outcome cannot be over stressed. Therefore, teacher's components such as use of instructional materials, students' assessment among others are crucial to the achievement of educational goals and objectives. Accordingly, Igoni (2020) concluded that the most significant component influencing students' learning is the teacher. Teachers stand in the contact of the transmission of knowledge, values and skills in the learning process. If the teacher is not effective, students under his learning programme cannot achieve academically. Secondary education is believed to be a weak connection in the education lane in many developing countries, even though an increasing number of children are going on to secondary schools (Kanishka and Sharma, 2006). As there are so many substandard schools today, the stakeholder should continue to orientate the general public on the great needs of investing in education because many schools are still endowed with ineffective in the quality of learning which is greatly affecting the students' academic outcome both at internal or external examination.

The role of a parent over a child at any given time cannot be over emphasized. The home background is very important to a child's growth and success in life. Parents are the most immediate relation of a child (Etheridge 2017). This is because parent in the home are children's first teacher, he gradually learns how to speak, listen, write and read which latter develop the child to achieve in totality. Oyewole and Oloyede (2019) stated that the influence of democratic parenting style on students' academic performance emphasizes the important role of parents in their children's academic outcome.

Nigeria in the recent times has made the growth of secondary education in the state a challenging process. Parents and all stakeholders in education sector have variously commented on the outcome of secondary school students. Investigation and reports from examining bodies like West Africa Examination Council(WAEC) and National Examination Council (NECO) revealed that a high percentage of secondary school students continue to perform poorly most especially in mathematics, English studies chemistry, physics and economics which are core subjects This is confirmed with the release of WAEC result for May/ June 2013 as quoted in the daily newspaper, "the West African Examination Council (WAEC) released results of the May/ June 2013 west African senior secondary certificate examination, with about 30% of the candidates making credit in English and Mathematics. Details of the results showed that the results of 81,573 candidates representing 5.29% were withheld. Despite the laudable efforts at improving students' outcome, it appears there has not been appreciable improvement over the years. The recent discussion of educational stakeholders is focused on educational standards while the nation's concern becomes more consistent following the recent result of students in the West African Senior School Certificate Examination.

Apparently, when untrained teachers engaged students for West African Senior School Certificate Examination (WASSCE), it is certain for the students to have poor grade in the examination. According to Nkeyemudim and Frank (2023), the government should find all possible means to retain experienced teachers who are willing to serve in order to contribute their

wealth of experience to improve the system. The Baguada Seminar Reports on Quantities and Qualities in Nigerian Education (NERC, 1980) as cited by Purwanto (2020) stated that the low quality of teachers will affect the competitiveness and quality of students also stated.

If teachers are apathetic, uncommitted, uninspired, lazy, unmotivated, immoral and anti-social, the whole nation is doomed. If teachers are ignorant in their disciplines and impart wrong information, this will lead to goal unachieved. The fact that substandard education contributes greatly to cases of examination malpractice that is now rampant in public examinations, as unpreparedness and fear of failure implore candidates into finding ways and strategies to cheat during an examination. Ogunsaju (2004), stated that the academic standard in all Nigerian educational institutions has fallen considerably below societal expectations.

Biseth et al. (2021) supported this when he stated that the decline in the quality of education cannot be avoided by anyone who is aware of the important role of education as a means for societal transformation growth and development. It is very vital to have enough and adequate human resources in terms of teacher's components for the teaching of all subjects in the school curriculum. Without the teachers as implementing component, the goals of education cannot be achieved. In order to achieve an equal society as stated in the Nigerian National Policy of Education (FRN, 2020), schools should be properly and uniformly equipped to promote sound and effective teaching. Suitable textbooks, qualified teachers, libraries which are adequate also should be provided for schools.

Scarcities of these, will constrain educational system from responding more fully to new demands. Teaching is not just a matter of teacher's talking and students listening, effective teaching involves interactive communication ways that are skillfully directed. In developed and developing countries, the quality of any worker in any organization is generally measured through obtained certificates as summed up by output (Asuku, 1999; Dahie et al, 2018). It has been proved that in many countries, teachers' certifications that are considered to be tally with student learning have become desirable targets of teacher education reform. Some of these reforms call for the professionalization of teacher education by upgrading it to graduate programmes, and regulating it through mechanisms of certification, and promotion that is conformed with standards (Darling-Hammond, Berry and Thorenson, 2001; Darling Hammond, Chung and Frelow; 2002; [Frank and Nkeyemudim 2023](#)).

The classroom is that space bounded by the wall and roof, which a teacher houses his students for the purpose of giving instruction to such students. In other words, it is a shelter for both teachers and learners so as to engage in educative interactive activities. Classroom management and control dictates the kind of relationship that exists between the teacher and the student during instructional activity and this ultimately determines the performance of students in school (Ahan, 2001). Management of classroom is one way to improve the learning of a student and to prevent problem in the academic outcome of the student, finding on classroom management has proven that a well-structured Classroom tends to improve student academic outcome (David-West 2017).

The student academic outcomes do not tally with great efforts and funds expended by the government and parents because of high level of failure in the external examinations. All educational planners and stakeholders are greatly worried about why the sector is producing graduates with poor results. The concern question is whether or not teachers in the public secondary schools are the most significant component of quality outcome in schools. Thus, this study will examine the following: teacher intending skills, teacher sex, teaching experience, teacher certificate, classroom management, teacher classroom and management conduct. The study also examined teachers' component and parental participation impact on senior secondary school student academic outcome.

Purpose of Study

The purpose of this study is to find out was to examine teacher component and parental participation impact on senior secondary school student academic outcome in Ifo local government area of Ogun state, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following questions were raised and answered in this study

What is the level of teacher component impact in secondary schools' student academic outcome in Ifo local government area of Ogun State, Nigeria?

What are the extents of parental participation impact in secondary schools student academic outcome in Ifo local government area of Ogun State, Nigeria?

Hypotheses

To guide this research, the following hypotheses were formulated and tested:

Ho1 There is no significant relationship between teacher certifications and secondary schools' student academic outcome in Ifo local government area of Ogun state, Nigeria.

Ho2 There is no significant relationship between teacher years of experience and secondary schools' student academic outcome in Ifo local government area of Ogun state, Nigeria.

Ho3 There is no significant relationship between parent participation and secondary schools' student academic outcome in Ifo local government area of Ogun state, Nigeria.

Ho4 There is no significant relationship between teacher necessary skills and secondary schools' student academic outcome in Ifo local government area of Ogun state, Nigeria. (Classroom management, planning, class control and so on).

Methodology

The study adopted descriptive survey research design of the ex-post facto type. The target population of the study covered teachers and students in some senior secondary schools in Ifo local government area of Ogun state. The sample that was used for the study was selected through simple random sampling procedure. The total number of schools sampled was 10. Fifty teachers in all the selected schools participated in the study while 200 students were sampled through stratified sampling technique. In all, 250 respondents were used for the study.

Instrument

The two research-designed instrument that was used for data collection: Teacher Component and Parental Participation Impact on Student Academic Outcome” (TCPPISAO) meant for the teachers and student academic outcome Test (SAOT) completed by the students and content validated. The Cronbach alpha reliability coefficient for student academic outcome Test (SAOT) was 0.83.

Findings and Discussion

The data collected were analyzed with Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient and regression analysis at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Ho1 There is no significant relationship between teacher certifications and secondary schools student academic outcome in Ifo local government area of Ogun state, Nigeria.

Table 1: Relationship between teacher certifications and student academic outcome

Variables	N	Mean	Std	Df	r	Sig	P
Academic outcome	200	18.13	5.115				
Teacher certification	50	16.8000	4.25092	248	.662**	.000	<.05

Table 1 displays the relationship between teacher certifications and student academic outcome, $r = 0.662$, $p < 0.05$. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore there was a significant relationship between teacher certifications and student academic outcome. This implies that an increase in teacher certification will increase the certainty for students to perform better.

Ho2 There is no significant relationship between teacher duration of experience and secondary schools' student academic outcome in Ifo local government area of Ogun state, Nigeria.

Table 2: Relationship between teacher duration of experience and student academic outcome

Variables	N	Mean	Std	Df	R	Sig	P
Academic outcome	200	18.13	5.115				
Teachers duration of experience	50	17.2800	3.99266	248	.679**.	.000	<.05

Table.2 displays the relationship between teachers duration of experience and students' academic outcome; $r = 0.679$, $p < 0.05$. Hence the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore there was a significant relationship between teacher duration of experience and student academic outcome. This implies that an increase in teacher duration of experience will increase the tendency for students to perform better.

Ho3 There is no significant relationship between parent participation and secondary schools' student academic outcome in Ifo local government area of Ogun state, Nigeria.

Table 3: Relationship between parental participation and student's academic outcome

Variables	N	Mean	Std	Df	R	Sig	P
Academic outcome	200	18.13	5.115				
Parental participation	50	16.3600	4.88567	248	.601**	.000	<.05

Table 3 reveals the relationship between parental participation and students' academic output; $r = 0.601$, $p < 0.05$. Hence the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore there was a significant relationship between parental participation and student's academic outcome. This implies that an increase in parental participation will increase the tendency for students to perform better.

Ho4 There is no significant relationship between teacher necessary skills and secondary schools' student academic outcome in Ifo local government area of Ogun state, Nigeria. (classroom management, planning, class control and so on). Table 4: Relationship between teacher necessary skills (classroom management, class control and planning of instructions) and student academic outcome

Variables	N	Mean	Std	Df	R	Sig	P
Academic outcome	200	18.13	5.115				
teacher necessary skills	50	17.5600	4.22798	248	.644**	.000	<.05

Table 4 displays the relationship between teacher necessary skills and students' academic outcome; $r = 0.644$, $p < 0.05$. Hence the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore there was a significant relationship between teacher necessary skills and students' academic outcome. This implies that an increase in teacher necessary skills will increase the tendency for students to perform better.

Discussion

The findings from hypothesis one displays there was a significant relationship between teacher certification and students' academic outcome. A significant correlation coefficient ($r = 0.662$) that was significant was found. The finding agreed with Hazan and Musa (2019) had proven that student outcome had a relationship with teacher components because when teachers did not perform their duties and functions, the students would not be able to learn well and achieve success. Also, the result of the study is in agreement with Huang and Moon (2009) documents that teacher certification responsible for about 40 to 60 percent of the variance in average of students' goals in assessment. The good performance was related to excellent instructions given by qualified teachers in addition to other inputs. Findings from hypothesis two showed there is a significant relationship between teachers' duration of experience and students' academic outcome. A positive correlation coefficient ($r = 0.679$) that was significant was found. This finding is explained in the context of the fact that an experienced teacher is more conversant with the curriculum he has been handling for years and all he needs to do is to adopt new methods in handling them. An experienced teacher is matured and is better adhere to teaching as a profession. This result agreed with what Hanushek et al (2005) cited by Amoli (2016) said that has been observed that there were significant relationship between teaching experience and students' academic outcome. A number of studies found teachers' duration of experience to positively correlate with students' goal. For example, Rivkin, Hanushek and Kain (2005) cited by Amoli (2016) showed that students of experienced teachers achieved better than students of new teachers (those with one to three years of experience). Furthermore, the result of the finding from hypothesis three showed there is a significant relationship between parental participation and student's academic outcome. A positive correlation coefficient ($r = 0.601$) that was significant was found. This result also supported the statement of McWayne (2005); that children who came from economically advantaged home receive much support at home that enhance their academic goal. There is fact that the positive relationship between parental impact, which is a yardstick of socio-economic status of parents and the academic progress of their children was also established by Lee and Sungur (2009); Oluwatelure (2010) cited by Babalola (2019) in their findings. The implication of the finding indicated that those students whose parents had higher expectations for their children's academic goal performed better from the beginning of their academic career and accelerated faster in their academic progress during the transition period of middle to high grades. Finding from hypothesis four displayed that there is a significant positive

relationship between teacher necessary skills. This finding agreed with the finding of Lusuwe (2007) that the management of discipline are requirement for effective classroom control. All teachers are responsible for managing discipline in their classroom. These findings strongly agree with the findings of Awoyemi (2002) cited by Adegbile (2018) that a significant relationship exists between teachers' experience and students' academic outcome. Also, as suggested by some researchers that teacher attribute and experience may not directly influence students' goal, but may do so indirectly. This implies that experience is highly valued in the teaching profession.

Conclusion

The study concluded that strongest determinant of students' academic outcome is teacher teaching experience, followed by teacher necessary skills, while other variables (parental participation, teacher certification and teacher sufficient) are not real determinant of student academic outcome in Ifo local government area of Ogun state. A greater academic progress can also be attained by students if their parents are much committed to the reality their children goals and aspiration. The study discovered that teacher long duration of teaching experience and teacher necessary skills correlated significantly with student academic outcome. This implies that every effort should be made to retain the more experienced teachers in the service while the less experienced teachers are also encouraged to learn from the experienced teachers; in addition, effective and efficient classroom management needs proactive teachers to instruct and communicate their effective academic expectations to their students.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

- i. The Federal Ministry of Education should ensure that adequate and sufficient facilities and equipment are provided. The availability of these facilities will improve the level of students' academic outcome.
- ii. Teachers should be implored to consistently attend workshops or seminars to deepening their teaching knowledge and understanding how to assess students learning in their various subjects.
- iii. Parents should be enlightened on the significance of consistent support of student education in schools through the Parent Teachers Association.
- iv. There is the need for teachers to be resourceful in instructional materials selection and utilization. The cost of production and maintenance of instructional materials should be reduced, especially the improvised materials.
- v. There is need for regular training and retraining of teachers to enhance the teaching and learning process.

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